

MODULE OF HOMEOMORPHISMS TO MODULE

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In this paper, after a concise presentation of the modules over rings as a generalization of vector space over the fields, their homeomorphisms are treated. Further builds R-module si R-module of morphisms of the modules.

Keywords:

R-module, left (right) R-module, abelian group, associative ring, R-homeomorphisms

THE MEANING OF THE R-MODULE, FEATURE

Let M be an non empty set of equipped with an internal algebraic action [2] marked with the symbol of collection $+$ and R an associative ring whatsoever [3]. A set M is also equipped with an algebraic external action [2] indicated by the multiplication symbol $\cdot$, which, when reflecting $R \times M$ in M , is referred to as the left multiplication in M with elements from R , whereas, when reflecting the $M \times R$ in M is called right multiplication in M with elements from R . In the first case the couple's image $(r, m) \in R \times M$ is written $r \cdot m$, in the second case the couple's image $(m, r) \in M \times R$ is written $m \cdot r$.

Definition 1.1 [1, 5, 6] In the above conditions, the left module above the R ring is called the structure $(M, +, \cdot)$, which has its own attributes:

$$\bullet (M, +) \text{ is an abelian group;} \quad (1)$$

$$\bullet \forall (r_1, r_2, m) \in R^2 \times M, r_1(r_2 m) = (r_1 r_2) m; \quad (2)$$

$$\bullet \forall (r, m_1, m_2) \in R \times M^2, r(m_1 + m_2) = r m_1 + r m_2; \quad (3)$$

$$\bullet \forall (r_1, r_2, m) \in R^2 \times M, (r_1 + r_2) m = r_1 m + r_2 m. \quad (4)$$

Definition 1.2. Under the above conditions, the right module above the R ring is called the structure $(M, +, \cdot)$, which has its own attributes:

$$\bullet (M, +) \text{ is an abelian group;} \quad (1')$$

$$\bullet \forall (m, r_1, r_2) \in M \times R^2, (m r_1) r_2 = m (r_1 r_2); \quad (2')$$

$$\bullet \forall (m_1, m_2, r) \in M^2 \times R, (m_1 + m_2) r = m_1 r + m_2 r; \quad (3')$$

$$\bullet \forall (m, r_1, r_2) \in M \times R^2, m (r_1 + r_2) = m r_1 + m r_2. \quad (4')$$

The left (right) module above the R ring is marked ${}_R M$ (M_R) and is called R -left module (right). If the left-hand module above R is also the right is called a *module* above the R ring, in short R -module.

If the ring has a single element 1_R (short 1) and the above-mentioned attributes for ${}_R M$ (M_R) is added the feature

$$\bullet \forall m \in M, 1 \cdot m = m (m \cdot 1 = m) \quad (5)$$

then the module ${}_R M$ (M_R) is called *the unitary left (right) module* above the R ring.

In ongoing, the R ring is associated and for a module on such a ring simple naming is used R -Module.

Below we will treat the R -modules, implying left R -modules, since the right R -modules are treated analogously.

THEOREM 1.1. A R -module M enjoys the following attributes:

$$\bullet \forall m \in M, 0_R \cdot m = 0_M; \quad (6)$$

$$\bullet \bullet \forall r \in R, r \cdot 0_M = 0_M; \quad (7)$$

$$\bullet \bullet \bullet \forall m \in M, \forall r \in R, (-r) \cdot m = r \cdot (-m) = -r \cdot m \in M. \quad (8)$$

Proof. Let r be a fixed element of the R ring and m any other element of the ${}_R M$ module. By Definition 1.1. we have $r \cdot m + 0_R \cdot m = (r + 0_R) \cdot m = r \cdot m$. On the other hand, by the additive group $(M, +)$, we have $r \cdot m + 0_M = r \cdot m$. From here $r \cdot m + 0_R \cdot m = r \cdot m + 0_M$, that gives $0_R \cdot m = 0_M$.

$$\bullet \bullet r \cdot 0_M = r \cdot (0_R \cdot m) = (r \cdot 0_R) \cdot m = 0_R \cdot m = 0_M.$$

$$\bullet \bullet \bullet r \cdot m + (-r) \cdot m = (r + (-r))m = 0_R \cdot m = 0_R \cdot m = 0_M \\ \Rightarrow (-r) \cdot m = -r \cdot m.$$

R-HOMEOMORPHISMS OF R-MODULES

Definition 2.1 [1,6] R -homomorphism (or R -morphism) of a R -module M in a R -module N is called any reflection $f: M \rightarrow N$ having attributes

$$\bullet f(m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1) + f(m_2), \forall m_1, m_2 \in M; \quad (9)$$

$$\bullet f(r \cdot m) = r \cdot f(m), \forall r \in R \text{ and } \forall m \in M \quad (10)$$

$$(\text{ose } f(m \cdot r) = f(m) \cdot r, \forall r \in R \text{ and } \forall m \in M).$$

If $M=N$, then the reflection f is called R -endomorphism in M .

THEOREM 2.1. For every two R -modules M, N , if the reflection $f: M \rightarrow N$ is a R -homomorphism, then

$$\bullet f(0_M) = 0_N, \quad (11)$$

$$\bullet f(-m) = -f(m), \forall m \in M, \quad (12)$$

$$\bullet f(m_1 - m_2) = f(m_1) - f(m_2), \forall m_1, m_2 \in M, \quad (13)$$

Proof. According to (6) and (10) we have

$$f(0_M) = f(0_R \cdot m) = 0_R \cdot f(m) = 0_N.$$

Further, according to (9),

$$0_N = f(0_M) = f(m + (-m)) = f(m) + f(-m),$$

that tells us $f(-m)$ is the symmetric of $f(m)$ in the group $(N, +)$, so $-f(m) = f(-m)$. Finally,

$$\begin{aligned} f(m_1 - m_2) &= f(m_1 + (-m_2)) = f(m_1) + f(-m_2) \\ &= f(m_1) + (-f(m_2)) = f(m_1) - f(m_2), \forall m_1, m_2 \in M. \end{aligned}$$

THEOREM 2.2. For each two R -modules M, N , reflection $p_0: M \rightarrow N$, defined by $p_0(m) = 0_N, \forall m \in M$, is the R -homomorphism of M to N .

Proof. From the above definition of reflection p_0 we have

$$p_0(m_1 + m_2) = 0_N = 0_N + 0_N = p_0(m_1) + p_0(m_2), \forall m_1, m_2 \in M,$$

which indicates that p_0 enjoys the attribute (9); we also have

$$p_0(r \cdot m) = 0_N = r \cdot 0_N = r \cdot p_0(m), \forall r \in R \text{ dhe } \forall m \in M,$$

which indicates that p_0 also enjoys the attribute (10).

THEOREM 2.3. Identical reflection $I_M: M \rightarrow M$ (e.g the reflection defined by $I_M(m) = m, \forall m \in M$ is an R -endomorphism in M .

Proof. From the above definition of the identical reflection I_M we have

$$I_M(m_1 + m_2) = m_1 + m_2 = I_M(m_1) + I_M(m_2), \forall m_1, m_2 \in M,$$

Indicating that the I_M enjoys the attribute (9); we also have

$$I_M(r \cdot m) = r \cdot m = r \cdot I_M(m), \forall r \in R \text{ dhe } \forall m \in M,$$

which indicates that I_M enjoys the attribute (10).

MODULE $Hom_R(M, N)$ OF R -HOMOMORPHISMS OF THE MODULES

The study of homomorphisms of modules bring to the construction of an important module, called the *homomorphism module*.

Let be given the R -module M and the R -module N . The set of R -homomorphisms from M to N is written $Hom_R(M, N)$.

Definition 3.1. Let be f, g two possible reflections from M to N and r an element of an R ring. Then:

1. Many of the reflection f with the g reflection, which is written $f + g$, is called reflection $f + g: M \rightarrow N$, defined by

$$(f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m), \forall m \in M. \quad (14)$$

2. The opposite reflection of f reflection, which is written $-f$, is called reflection $-f: M \rightarrow N$, defined by

$$(-f)(m) = -f(m), \forall m \in M. \quad (15)$$

3. The left product of the reflection f with the element $r \in R$, which is written $r \cdot f$, is called the reflection $r \cdot f : M \rightarrow N$, defined by

$$(r \cdot f)(m) = r \cdot f(m), \forall m \in M. \quad (16)$$

An analogy is given to the meaning and the right production $f \cdot r$ such that $(f \cdot r)(m) = f(m) \cdot r, \forall m \in M$.

THEOREM 3.1. If the reflections f, g are R -homomorphisms from M to N then:

$$1. \quad f+g \in \text{Hom}_R(M, N), \quad (17)$$

otherwise, their amount $f+g$ is a R -homomorphism from M to N ;

$$2. \quad -f \in \text{Hom}_R(M, N), \quad (18)$$

otherwise, the reverse reflection $-f$ is a R -homomorphism from M to N ;

$$3. \quad \text{For each } r \in R, \text{ where } R \text{ is commutative,} \\ r \cdot f \in \text{Hom}_R(M, N), \quad (19)$$

otherwise, the left (right) production of f reflection with elements from R is a R -homomorphism from M to N .

Proof.

1. Since the reflections f, g are R -homomorphisms from M to N , then

$$\begin{aligned} (f+g)(m_1+m_2) &\stackrel{(14)}{=} f(m_1+m_2) + g(m_1+m_2) \\ &\stackrel{(9)}{=} [f(m_1) + f(m_2)] + [g(m_1) + g(m_2)] \\ &= [f(m_1) + g(m_1)] + [f(m_2) + g(m_2)] \\ &\stackrel{(14)}{=} (f+g)(m_1) + (f+g)(m_2), \forall m_1, m_2 \in M, \end{aligned}$$

which shows that $f+g$ enjoys the attribute (9); we also have

$$\begin{aligned} (f+g)(rm) &\stackrel{(14)}{=} f(rm) + g(rm) \\ &\stackrel{(10)}{=} rf(m) + rg(m) \\ &= r[f(m) + g(m)] \\ &\stackrel{(14)}{=} r[(f+g)(m)], \forall r \in R \text{ dhe } \forall m \in M, \end{aligned}$$

which shows that $f+g$ enjoys the attribute (10). Consequently $f+g \in \text{Hom}_R(M, N)$

2. Reflection f is R -homomorphism from M to N , therefore

$$\begin{aligned} (-f)(m_1+m_2) &\stackrel{(15)}{=} -f(m_1+m_2) \stackrel{(12)}{=} f(-(m_1+m_2)) = f(-(m_1)+(-m_2)) \\ &\stackrel{(9)}{=} f(-m_1)+f(-m_2) \stackrel{(12)}{=} (-f(m_1))+(-f(m_2)) \stackrel{(15)}{=} (-f)(m_1)+(-f)(m_2), \forall m_1, m_2 \in M, \end{aligned}$$

which shows that $-f$ enjoys the attribute (9); Also, having in mind and (8) we have

$$\begin{aligned} (-f)(r \cdot m) &\stackrel{(12)}{=} f(-r \cdot m) \stackrel{(8)}{=} f(r \cdot (-m)) \stackrel{(10)}{=} r \cdot f(-m) \stackrel{(12)}{=} r \cdot [-f(m)] \\ &\stackrel{(15)}{=} r \cdot [(-f)(m)], \forall r \in R \text{ dhe } \forall m \in M, \end{aligned}$$

which shows that $-f$ enjoys even the attribute (10).

3. We also have

$$\begin{aligned} (r \cdot f)(m_1 + m_2) &\stackrel{(16)}{=} r \cdot f(m_1 + m_2) \stackrel{(9)}{=} r \cdot [f(m_1) + f(m_2)] = r \cdot f(m_1) + r \cdot f(m_2) \\ &\stackrel{(16)}{=} (r \cdot f)(m_1) + (r \cdot f)(m_2), \forall m_1, m_2 \in M, \end{aligned}$$

showing that $r \cdot f$ has its attribute (9); also, knowing that the R ring is commutative we have

$$\begin{aligned} (r \cdot f)(\rho m) &\stackrel{(16)}{=} r \cdot f(\rho m) \stackrel{(10)}{=} r \cdot [\rho f(m)] = (r \rho) \cdot f(m) = (\rho r) \cdot f(m) \\ &\stackrel{(16)}{=} \rho \cdot [r \cdot f(m)] = \rho \cdot [(r \cdot f)(m)], \forall \rho \in R \text{ dhe } \forall m \in M, \end{aligned}$$

which shows that $r \cdot f$ also enjoys attribute (10).

Definition 3.2. R -homomorphism $f+g: M \rightarrow N$ is called R -homomorphism $f: M \rightarrow N$ with R -homomorphism $g: M \rightarrow N$, R -homomorphism $-f$ is called the opposite R -homomorphism $f: M \rightarrow N$, but R -homomorphism $r \cdot f$ ($f \cdot r$), when R is commutative, is called left (right) production of R -homomorphism $f: M \rightarrow N$ with element $r \in R$

Through this definition, they are introduced into the set $Hom_R(M, N)$ action of addition $+$ and left (right) multiplication, which make it algebra $(Hom_R(M, N), +, \cdot)$ with two actions.

THEOREM 3.2. If the R ring is commutative, then the algebra $(Hom_R(M, N), +, \cdot)$ of R -homeomorphisms from M to N is the R -left(right) module.

Proof. We show that they satisfy the conditions (1), (2), (3), (4) of Definition 1.1. of a left R -module.

(1) From the above it is easy to see that:

- $\forall f, g, h \in Hom_R(M, N), (f + g) + h = f + (g + h);$
- $\forall f \in Hom_R(M, N), f + p_0 = f;$
- $\forall f \in Hom_R(M, N), f + (-f) = p_0;$
- $\forall f, g \in Hom_R(M, N), f + g = g + f,$

indicating that $Hom_R(M, N), +$ is an abelian group.

(2) $\forall (r_1, r_2, f) \in R^2 \times Hom_R(M, N)$, writing $g = r_2 \cdot f$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} [r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot f)](m) &\stackrel{(16)}{=} (r_1 \cdot g)(m) \stackrel{(16)}{=} r_1 \cdot g(m) = r_1 \cdot [r_2 \cdot f(m)] = r_1 \cdot [r_2 \cdot f(m)] \\ &\stackrel{(10)}{=} r_1 \cdot [f(r_2 \cdot m)] \stackrel{(10)}{=} f(r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot m)) \stackrel{(10)}{=} f((r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot m) = (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot f(m) \\ &\stackrel{(16)}{=} [(r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot f](m), \forall m \in M, \end{aligned}$$

which indicates that $r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot f) = (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot f$.

(3) $\forall (r, f, g) \in R \times [Hom_R(M, N)]^2$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} [r \cdot (f+g)](m) & \stackrel{(16)}{=} r \cdot [(f+g)(m)] \stackrel{(14)}{=} r \cdot [f(m)+g(m)] = r \cdot f(m) + r \cdot g(m) \\ & \stackrel{(16)}{=} (r \cdot f)(m) + (r \cdot g)(m) \stackrel{(14)}{=} (r \cdot f + r \cdot g)(m), \quad \forall m \in M, \end{aligned}$$

which indicates that $r \cdot (f+g) = r \cdot f + r \cdot g$.

(4) $\forall (r_1, r_2, f) \in R^2 \times \text{Hom}_R(M, N)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} [(r_1+r_2) \cdot f](m) & \stackrel{(16)}{=} (r_1+r_2) \cdot f(m) \stackrel{(10)}{=} f((r_1+r_2)m) = f(r_1m+r_2m) \stackrel{(9)}{=} f(r_1m) + f(r_2m) \\ & \stackrel{(10)}{=} r_1 \cdot f(m) + r_2 \cdot f(m) \stackrel{(16)}{=} (r_1 \cdot f)(m) + (r_2 \cdot f)(m) \stackrel{(9)}{=} (r_1 \cdot f + r_2 \cdot f)(m), \quad \forall m \in M, \end{aligned}$$

which indicates that $(r_1+r_2) \cdot f = r_1 \cdot f + r_2 \cdot f$.

Analogously it is shown that $(\text{Hom}_R(M, N), +, \cdot)$ is the right R -module when $\cdot$ is right multiplication with elements from R .

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